

On the potential benefits of using GPUs for atomistic MD simulations using LAMMPS

Hariprasath Ganesan¹

¹Institute of Material Systems Modeling, Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon, Geesthacht, Germany.

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Abstract

This report presents the performance results of classical Molecular dynamics simulations using many-body interatomic potentials for metallic systems on heterogeneous CPU-GPU architecture. Two different simulation scenarios (short(1 ps) and long (900 ps)) have been performed and compared for CPU only and CPU-GPU configurations to quantify GPU performance contribution. In both scenarios, GPUs made significant performance speedup by a factor of 20. Furthermore, different computational resource configurations were compared to assess the influence of communication overhead, latency, proximity, and workload. The comparisons suggest an optimal choice of CPU/GPU ratio and distributed workload (load balancing) yield the best performance for the investigated simulations on heterogenous CPU-GPU architecture.

1 Hardware

The in-house cluster facility strand [1] provides high-performance computing resources to cater to the demands of computational research activities. Our cluster has several compute nodes each consisting of 48 cores (24 x 2 sockets) based on 2.1 GHz Intel Xeon Platinum Skylake architecture [2] with Omni-Path high-speed network. Among them, 25 nodes provide the hardware capability to use data-center GPUs. This performance analysis was realized on some dedicated test resources on our cluster [1] with 23 heterogeneous nodes (15 nodes with NVIDIA Tesla [3] V100 GPU (16 GB RAM) + 8 nodes with GPUs (32 GB RAM) from the same vendor and generation) offering the CPU-GPU compute capability. There are two major classifications of such heterogeneous nodes; the former consists of 1 GPU per 48 CPUs, and the latter with 2 GPUs per 48 CPUs.

2 Performance Analysis

2.1 LAMMPS capabilities for GPUs

A Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) is a classical Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation code dedicated to material modeling [4, 5]. LAMMPS enables the realization of MD simulations in parallel mode on multi-core CPU architecture and on hardware equipped with GPUs. Thanks to the accelerator packages bundled with LAMMPS, they offer several ways to accelerate the computational performance of the MD simulations by exploiting the state-of-the-art target architecture. Among them, two options are available for NVIDIA GPUs that are currently available on our strand cluster: GPU package [6] and Kokkos package [7]. For our performance study, the Kokkos acceleration package was selected for three reasons. First, compared to the GPU package, Kokkos contain a large portion of LAMMPS core modules (e.g., force routines, integrators, and atom styles), which can exploit GPU parallelization. Second, Kokkos provides an abstraction to allow the application kernel to run on different hardware; however, it is optimized for a specific architecture. Thus, it guarantees the performance portability of LAMMPS to any future architecture in a consistent way. Third, kokkos supports different back-end languages such as CUDA, OpenMP, or Pthreads; therefore, the same executable shall be launched in different parallelization modes (multi-core CPUs, multi-threading, and GPU).

2.2 MD simulations

The cubical simulation domain has an edge length of 20 nm with 636566 atoms, representing nanocrystalline intermetallic Titanium Aluminides (TiAl) system (like the previously reported Simplified Atomistic Models (SAM) reported in our work [8]). For the interatomic interactions, we considered the embedded atom method (EAM)[9] type potential developed by Zope and Mishin for TiAl [10]. We performed two dynamics simulation scenarios: 1.) NVE simulations for 1 ps with minimal file IO, and 2.) two-stage NPT simulations for 900 ps with considerable file IO, as encountered in the production run. Note that we considered the same simulation domain for the two scenarios mentioned for comparison and brevity.

For each simulation scenario, different hardware configurations were performed that are broadly classified into two modes: 1.) CPU-only mode and 2.) heterogeneous CPU-GPU mode. In particular, several combinations were tested for the heterogeneous CPU-GPU mode to identify the optimal choice and understand the factors affecting the performance. The different configurations considered in CPU-GPU mode were represented using a special notation $N_{nodes} : N_{CPUs} : CPUs/node : GPUs/node$. Here, the four indices represent the nodes count, CPUs count, allocated CPUs per node, and allocated GPUs per node, respectively. Such different configurations were aimed to shed light on the influence of various factors, namely CPU/GPU ratio, load balance, resource proximity, communication overhead, and latency; thus, enabling an optimal choice of configurations to harness the performance for the target architecture. For each simulation, two quantities were obtained: 1.) wall time with an

(a) Wall time

(b) Performance projection

Figure 1: Performance analysis of short simulations (1 ps) scenario for different CPU-GPU configurations and CPU-only (inset) mode.

average timing breakdown of a message passing interface (MPI) task, and 2.) performance projection resulting from the simulation statistics. Note that the timing breakdown has several components: modify (contribution from integrators and user computations), interatomic (non-bonded force computation), and neigh.list (neighbor list construction), communications (inter-processor communication of atoms/properties), output (statistics and snapshot files), and others (the rest).

2.2.1 Short simulations: 1 ps

Key observations:

For the CPU-only (mode 1) simulations (until 16 CPUs), the wall time reduces approximately by a factor of $(1/N)$, where N represents the total CPUs used for MPI parallelization (Fig. 1). Note for mode 1; the timing breakdown plot shows that the interatomic (force) computation module dominates the performance irrespective of N . On the other hand, for CPU-GPU mode, several configurations identified by the respective notations were tested. For the configuration 1:1:1:1 using the CPU/GPU=1 ratio, the simulation wall time was reduced by two orders of magnitude when

compared to the simulation without GPU. Simulations (1:1:1:2) with reduced ratio CPU/GPU=0.5 show some considerable speedup of 28%. Nevertheless, a significant performance drop was observed when the GPU resource (1:1:1:2 (RS - Resource Sharing)) is shared between two independent simulations at a given time. Thus, it is advisable to avoid resource sharing when possible to exploit better performance. For simulations (2:2:1:1) with a ratio CPU/GPU=1 and distributed workload between two nodes show performance improvement compared to simulations on a single node. Also, in this case, resource sharing affected the performance. Remember the two types of heterogeneous nodes available on our strand cluster: 1.) 48 CPUs + 1 GPU, 2.) 48 CPUs + 2 GPU. Simulations with the CPU/GPU>1 ratio affect the performance significantly due to high latency, traffic between host/GPU, and resource sharing. Altogether, the configuration (2:4:2:2) exhibited the best performance in scenario 1. There exist four crucial factors behind its performance: 1.) CPU/GPU=1, 2.) optimal load balance, 3.) No resource sharing, and 4.) resource affinity (proximity). However, it's hard to generalize these factors based solely on the simulations performed in scenario 1; therefore, we will consider much longer simulations (900 ps) in the following part. The subfigure (Fig. 1 b) shows the performance projection of the short simulations for various configurations. Theoretically, the performance projection should give an inverse trend of simulation wall time. Nevertheless, it gives us a reasonable quantification to plan large/long MD simulations for the available resources. Here, the optimal CPU-GPU configuration (2:4:2:2) showed a speedup by a factor of 20 against 16 CPUs-only simulations.

2.2.2 Long simulations: 900 ps

Key observations:

The long simulations (Fig. 2) for different configurations preserved similar performance behavior and trends compared to short simulations scenarios. Interestingly, the four crucial factors (CPU/GPU, optimal load balance, no resource sharing, and resource proximity) play a decisive role in the performance of heterogeneous CPU-GPU mode. Unlike short simulations, the interatomic (force) computation becomes decisive not only for the CPU-only mode but also for the CPU-GPU mode. In contrast, the optimal configuration (2:4:2:2) reduced the computation time of expensive modifications (integration, thermostat). In comparison to 8 CPUs (CPU only mode), 4 CPUs - 4 GPUS (2:4:2:2) configuration provides a speedup by a factor of 20, which is significant. As mentioned earlier, this configuration (2:4:2:2) also satisfies the four crucial factors for the long simulations. A higher CPU/GPU ratio leads to a deteriorating performance. The peak performance of the optimal configuration shows a projection of 8 ns/day, which is a factor of approximately 8 compared to simulations with 32 CPUs only mode.

No GPU accelerated production simulations of creep deformation:

The models consist of 7.56×10^6 atoms for our recent creep production simulations of Microstructure Informed Atomistic Models (MIAMs) ($M_5 - M_8$) [8]. These simulations used 216 CPUs on our strand cluster with no GPU acceleration, which provided a performance projection of 0.529 ns/day

(a) Wall time

(b) Performance projection

Figure 2: Performance analysis of long simulations (900 ps) scenario for different CPU-GPU configurations and CPU-only (inset) mode.

(comparable to the long simulations scenario considered in this benchmark study).

GPU accelerated production simulations of creep deformation:

MIAM M_7 has been repeated using the optimal tested configuration of 4 CPUs - 4 GPUs (2:4:2:2) to understand GPU's performance boost better. The performance projection was estimated to be 0.6 ns/day (slightly higher than CPUs only mode). It is worth emphasizing that the achieved performance was significant considering the atoms count (7.5×10^6) and utilized computing resources (4 CPU-GPU pairs vs. 216 CPUs). Intuitively, increasing the CPU-GPU pairs could increase the performance by one order of magnitude. This gives us a realistic estimate that besides the four crucial factors, the maximum atoms per CPU-GPU pair could play a role in determining the performance for extremely long/large MD simulations.

2.2.3 General discussion:

The applications of classical MD simulations witnessed widespread adoptions, encompassing different topical areas of materials science spanning polymers, metals, alloys, glasses, ceramics, and 2D materials. Some key areas of research using MD in metallic materials include microstructure and mechanical behavior at the nanoscale [11], kinetic effects like diffusion [12], radiation damage in nuclear

reactor walls [13], Hall-Petch effects of nanocrystalline systems [14], crack propagation [15], and time-dependent deformation behavior [8]. Despite these broad applications, MD simulations are inherently limited in the length and time scale of the physical phenomena they address. The length scale limitations could be overcome by spatially dividing the computational domain into several subdomains, each solved by an individual CPU [16]. Overcoming time scale limitations could take accelerated MD techniques [17] or highly parallel coupled MD/MC approaches [18–20]. It is worth noting that the high computational cost in a classical MD simulation stems from the expensive force computations associated with potential energy evaluation. Some of the core developers of LAMMPS reported the computational aspects of deploying the many-body interatomic potentials and the associated performance bottlenecks [21]. The combination of advanced GPU hardware and efficient implementations of acceleration packages [6, 7] available in LAMMPS offers a new route to realize the faster computation of large-scale MD simulations.

3 Summary

LAMMPS MD simulations enable the possibility of harnessing the benefits of modern GPUs like the NVIDIA Tesla mounted on our strand clusters. The performance benchmark studies of two simulation scenarios (short and long) showed a speedup by a factor of 20 when such simulations were executed in heterogeneous CPU-GPU mode. Besides the significant performance boost, this study suggests considering five crucial factors for optimal performance: 1. CPU/GPU=1, 2. optimal workload balance across nodes, 3. avoiding resource sharing, 4. ensuring resources physical proximity, and 5. N_{atoms} per CPU-GPU pair. Thus, having several nodes equipped with GPUs for atomistic simulations is optimal. It is desirable to configure the compute nodes with a low CPU/GPU ratio (ideally less than 5, unlike the current ratio of 48) because the performance benchmark suggests an optimal CPU/GPU ratio of 1 to avoid the probability of resource sharing and idle resources.

Note that the insights from this performance investigation hold for classical EAM potentials typically used for metallic systems and alloys in LAMMPS. Therefore, it is worth performing a system-specific investigation with appropriate potential to achieve the optimal performance of heterogeneous CPU/GPU. It is foreseen that GPU acceleration could also benefit electronic structure DFT simulations, ML high-throughput, and atomistic MD simulations simulating both slow phenomena and encompassing large atomistic models describing complex microstructure.

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